

INVARIANT MANIFOLDS OF THE STOCHASTIC BENJAMIN-BONA-MAHONY EQUATION

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ABSTRACT. This paper studies the stochastic analogue of the Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation, which is a model of long waves in nonlinear dispersive media with dissipation, as well as the solvability and solution stability of this equation. To this end, the stochastic Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation is considered as a special case of a stochastic semilinear Sobolev-type equation. The paper also establishes the type of phase space defined as the set of admissible initial data and proves the existence of infinite-dimensional stable and finite-dimensional unstable invariant manifolds of the stochastic Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation.

Introduction

When studying mathematical models of long waves propagating in one direction in dissipative and dispersive media, the following equation was obtained [1]:

$$\lambda z_t - z_{xxt} = \nu z_{xx} - zz_x. \quad (0.1)$$

Equation (0.1) is commonly referred to as the Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation. This equation was studied as an improvement of the Korteweg-de Vries equation when constructing a model of small-amplitude surface gravity waves. [2] and [3] considered equation (0.1) as a one-dimensional case of the Oskolkov equation system. They investigated the solvability of the initial-boundary value problem for the Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation at $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+$. [4] studied this problem at an arbitrary value of $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$. They showed that its phase space is the union of two connected components. The review paper [5] presents results on the stability of the Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation. The purpose of this paper is to study a stochastic analogue of the Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation. To this end, we consider equation (0.1) as a special case of a semilinear stochastic Sobolev-type equation

$$L \overset{\circ}{\eta} = M\eta + N(\eta). \quad (0.2)$$

Here, the stochastic process acts as the desired quantity, its derivative is considered as a Nelson–Glicklikh derivative [6], L and M are linear and bounded operators, and N is a nonlinear operator. The number of articles studying stochastic Sobolev-type equations has been constantly increasing, [7] considered a linear equation of

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form (0.2) (i.e., at $N \equiv \mathbb{O}$) in the case of a relatively bounded operator, [8] a relatively sectorial operator, and [9] a relatively radial operator. [10] investigates multipoint problems for equation (0.2), while [11] studies high-order stochastic Sobolev-type equations. [12] considers the nonlinear equation

$$L \overset{\circ}{\eta} = M(\eta). \quad (0.3)$$

where L is the linear operator and M is the nonlinear operator demonstrating the conditions for the existence of the solutions to equation (0.2).

In this paper, we follow the results of [12] on the solvability of nonlinear equations of form (0.2), as well as [13] and [14] on the stability of semilinear Sobolev-type equations. The rest of the paper consists of three sections. The first section defines the concepts of a random variable, a stochastic process, the Nelson–Glicklikh derivative, random \mathbf{K} -variables, and \mathbf{K} -”noises” spaces. The second section considers the solvability of equations of form (0.2) and establishes the existence of stable and unstable invariant manifolds. The third section applies the results of the second section to the stochastic Benjamin–Bona–Mahony equation and shows the existence of solutions to this equation and their stability in terms of invariant manifolds.

1. Spaces of random \mathbf{K} -variables and \mathbf{K} -”noises”

Let \mathbf{CL}_2 be the space of continuous stochastic processes $\eta = \eta(t, \omega)$ with the norm

$$\|\eta\|^2 = \sup_{t \in \mathcal{J}} (\mathbf{D}\eta(t, \omega)),$$

with the interval $\mathcal{J} \subset \mathfrak{R}$. Let us fix $\eta \in \mathbf{CL}_2$ and $t \in \mathcal{J}$. The σ -algebra generated by the random value $\eta(t)$ will be denoted by \mathcal{N}_t^η . \mathbf{E}_t^η denotes the conditional expectation function $\mathbf{E}(\cdot | \mathcal{N}_t^\eta)$, where \mathcal{N}_t^η is the σ -algebra generated by the random value $\eta(t)$.

Definition 1.1. [6] Let $\eta \in \mathbf{CL}_2$. The Nelson–Glicklikh derivative $\overset{\circ}{\eta}$ of the stochastic process η at the point $t \in \mathcal{J}$ is the random value

$$\overset{\circ}{\eta} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0+} \mathbf{E}_t^\eta \left(\frac{\eta(t + \Delta t, \cdot) - \eta(t, \cdot)}{\Delta t} \right) + \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0+} \mathbf{E}_t^\eta \left(\frac{\eta(t, \cdot) - \eta(t - \Delta t, \cdot)}{\Delta t} \right) \right),$$

if there is a limit in the sense of a uniform metric on \mathbb{R} .

The Nelson–Glicklikh derivative $\overset{\circ}{\eta}(\cdot, \omega)$ exists in the interval \mathcal{J} (almost in the interval \mathcal{J}), if it exists at all points (at almost all points) of the interval \mathcal{J} . Let us consider a set of stochastic processes, where the trajectories are almost certainly Nelson–Glicklikh differentiable by \mathcal{J} to the l -th order, and introduce the norm:

$$\|\eta\|_{\mathbf{C}^l \mathbf{L}_2}^2 = \sup_{t \in \mathcal{J}} \sum_{k=1}^l \mathbf{D} \overset{\circ}{\eta}^k(t, \omega),$$

where $\overset{\circ}{\eta}^0 \equiv \eta$. We let $\mathbf{C}^l \mathbf{L}_2$ denote the obtained Banach space, $l \in \mathbb{N}$, and call it the space of differentiable ”noises” (see [6]–[9]).

Let the spaces \mathfrak{U} and \mathfrak{F} be separable Hilbert spaces. We use $\{\varphi_k\}$ and $\{\psi_k\}$ to denote the orthonormal basis with respect to the corresponding scalar product in \mathfrak{U}

and \mathfrak{F} . We chose a sequence of real numbers $\mathbf{K} = \{\lambda_k \in \mathbb{R}_+\}$, where $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 < \infty$, and a sequence of uniformly bounded random values $\{\xi_k\} \subset \mathbf{L}_2$ ($\{\zeta_k\} \subset \mathbf{L}_2$). Let us construct a \mathfrak{U} -digit random \mathbf{K} -value $\xi = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \xi_k \varphi_k$ and a \mathfrak{F} -digit random \mathbf{K} -value $\zeta = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \zeta_k \psi_k$. We complete the linear envelope of the random \mathfrak{U} -digit \mathbf{K} -values in the norm $\|\xi\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 \mathbf{D}\xi_k$, and the linear envelope of the random \mathfrak{F} -digit \mathbf{K} -values in the norm $\|\zeta\|_{\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^2 \mathbf{D}\zeta_k$. We obtain the Hilbert spaces of \mathfrak{U} -digit random \mathbf{K} -values $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ and \mathfrak{F} -digit random \mathbf{K} -values $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$.

Notably, different monotonic positive sequences \mathbf{K} can be chosen for the spaces \mathfrak{U} and \mathfrak{F} . For example, the sequences $\mathbf{K} = \{\lambda'_k\}$ and $\mathbf{K} = \{\lambda''_k\}$ are such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda'_k}{\lambda''_k} = \text{const.}$ Then, the random \mathbf{K} -values will be as follows $\xi = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda'_k \xi_k \varphi_k$, $\zeta = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda''_k \zeta_k \psi_k$.

Let the interval $(\varepsilon, \tau) \subset \mathbb{R}$ and $\{\xi_k\}$ be a sequence from $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{L}_2$. A *continuous stochastic \mathbf{K} -process* is the expression

$$\eta(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \xi_k(t) \varphi_k, \quad (1.1)$$

if the series converges uniformly in the norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2}$ on any compact set in (ε, τ) , and the trajectories of the process $\eta = \eta(t)$ are almost certainly continuous. $\mathbf{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$ denotes the space of continuous stochastic \mathbf{K} -processes. The continuous stochastic \mathbf{K} -process $\eta = \eta(t)$ is called *continuously Nelson–Glicklikh differentiable* on (ε, τ) if the series

$$\overset{\circ}{\eta}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \overset{\circ}{\xi}_k(t) \varphi_k \quad (1.2)$$

converges uniformly on any compact set in (ε, τ) in the norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2}$, and the trajectories of the process $\overset{\circ}{\eta} = \overset{\circ}{\eta}(t)$ are almost certainly continuous. $\mathbf{C}^l(\mathcal{J}, \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$ denotes the space of stochastic \mathbf{K} -processes continuously differentiable up to the order $l \in \mathbb{N}$.

2. Stochastic Sobolev type equations

Let \mathfrak{U} and \mathfrak{F} be separable Hilbert spaces, and the operators $L, M : \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ be linear and continuous. The following lemma is correct.

Lemma 2.1. *The operator A acting from the space \mathfrak{U} to the space \mathfrak{F} is linear and continuous if and only if the same operator A acting from the space of \mathfrak{U} -digit random \mathbf{K} -values $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{K}_2$ to the space of \mathfrak{F} -digit random \mathbf{K} -values $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{K}_2$ is linear and continuous.*

Based on lemma 2.1 we transfer the results [15, ch. 3] to the space of random \mathbf{K} -values. The set $\rho^L(M) = \{\mu \in \mathbb{C} : (\mu L - M)^{-1} \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2; \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)\}$ is called the *L-resolvent set*, and the set the *L-spectrum of the operator M*. If the *L-spectrum* of the operator *M* is bounded, the operator *M* is called the *(L, σ)-bounded operator*.

Remark 2.2. The concept of the *(L, σ)-boundedness* of the operator *M* with the operators *L, M : U → F* coincides with the concept of the *(L, σ)-boundedness* of the operator *M* with the operators *L, M : U_KL₂ → F_KL₂*.

For the *(L, σ)-boundedness* of the operator *M*, we can construct the following projections

$$P = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\gamma} (\mu L - M)^{-1} L d\mu \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2), \quad (2.1)$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\gamma} L(\mu L - M)^{-1} d\mu \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2). \quad (2.2)$$

Here, $\sigma^L(M)$ lies in an area bounded by the contour $\gamma \subset \mathbb{C}$. Projections (2.1), (2.2) split the spaces $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 = \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2 \oplus \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 = \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2 \oplus \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$, where $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2$ ($\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$) = $\ker P$ ($\text{im}P$), $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2$ ($\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$) = $\ker Q$ ($\text{im}Q$). L_k (M_k) denotes the restriction of the operator *L* (*M*) on $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^k\mathbf{L}_2$, $k = 0, 1$.

If the operator *M* is *(L, σ)-bounded* and the operators $L_k(M_k) : \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^k\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^k\mathbf{L}_2$, $k = 0, 1$, are linear continuous operators, there exist linear continuous operators $M_0^{-1} : \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^0\mathbf{L}_2$, $L_1^{-1} : \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$. Let us consider the operators $H = L_0^{-1}M_0$ and $S = L_1^{-1}M_1$. If the operator *M* is *(L, σ)-bounded* and $H \equiv \mathbb{O}$, $p = 0$ or $H^p \neq \mathbb{O}$, $H^{p+1} \equiv \mathbb{O}$, it is called an *(L, p)-bounded operator*. Let us turn to the existence of solutions to equation (0.2).

Let $\mathcal{J} = \{0\} \cup \mathbb{R}_+$. The stochastic \mathbf{K} -process $\eta \in \mathbf{C}^1(\mathcal{J}; \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$ is called a *solution to equation (2)* if all its trajectories almost certainly satisfy equation (0.2) for all $t \in \mathcal{J}$. The solution $\eta = \eta(t)$ to equation (0.2) is called the *solution to the Cauchy problem*

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} (\eta(t) - \eta_0) = 0, \quad (2.3)$$

if equality (2.3) is satisfied for a random \mathbf{K} -value $\eta_0 \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2$.

Definition 2.3. The set $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2 \subset \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2$ is called the *stochastic phase space* of equation (0.2) if

- (i) every trajectory of the solution $\eta = \eta(t)$ to equation (0.2) almost certainly lies in $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2$, i.e. $\eta(t) \in \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2, t \in \mathbb{R}$, for almost all trajectories;
- (ii) for $\eta_0 \in \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{L}}\mathbf{L}_2$ there almost certainly exists a solution to problems (0.2), (2.3).

At a fixed $\omega \in \Omega$ the solution to equation (0.2) is the trajectory $\eta = \eta(t)$, it almost certainly lies in the set

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{cases} \{\eta \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 : (\mathbb{I} - Q)(M\eta + N(\eta)) = 0\}, & \ker L \neq \{0\}; \\ \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, & \ker L = \{0\}. \end{cases}$$

As mentioned in the introduction, [12] studied the solvability of problems (0.3), (2.3) and showed, with some assumptions, the existence of a resolving semigroup defined on the set \mathbf{M} .

Theorem 2.4. [12] *Let the operator M be (L, p) -bounded, the operator $N \in C^1(\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$, and the set \mathbf{M} be a simple Banach C^1 -manifold at the point $\eta_0 \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$. Then the set \mathbf{M} is the phase space of equation (0.2).*

Remark 2.5. According to theorem 2.4, the phase space of the linear equation

$$L \overset{\circ}{\eta} = M\eta \quad (2.4)$$

is the space $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$. Moreover, if there is the operator $L^{-1} \in \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2; \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$, then $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 = \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$.

Now let us turn to the stability of equation (0.2). Let the L -spectrum of the operator M be such that:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma^L(M) &= \sigma_r^L(M) \cup \sigma_l^L(M), \\ \sigma_r^L(M) &= \{\mu \in \sigma^L(M) : \operatorname{Re}\mu > 0 \ (\operatorname{Re}\mu > 0)\}, \\ \sigma_r^L(M) &\neq \emptyset. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.5)$$

Then there exist projections

$$P_{l(r)} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\gamma_{r(l)}} (\mu L - M)^{-1} L d\mu,$$

where the contour $\gamma_{r(l)}$ bounds the area containing $\sigma_r^L(M)$ ($\sigma_l^L(M)$) and lies on the right (left) half-plane.

Definition 2.6. The subspace $\mathbf{I}^{s(u)}$ of the phase space $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ of equation (2.4) is called a *stable (unstable) invariant space* of equation (2.4) if

(i) at any $\eta_0 \in \mathbf{I}^{s(u)}$ the solution to problem (0.2), (2.3) $\eta(0) = \eta_0$ for equation (2.4) $\eta \in C^1(\mathbb{R}; \mathbf{I}^{s(u)})$.

(ii) there exist constants $N_k \in \mathbb{R}_+$, $\nu_k \in \mathbb{R}_+$, $k = 1, 2$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\eta^1(t)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} &\leq N_1 e^{-\nu_1(s-t)} \|\eta^1(s)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \quad \text{for } s \geq t \\ (\|\eta^2(t)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} &\leq N_2 e^{-\nu_2(t-s)} \|\eta^2(s)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \quad \text{for } t \geq s) \end{aligned}$$

where $\eta^1 = \eta^1(t) \in \mathbf{I}^s$ ($\eta^2 = \eta^2(t) \in \mathbf{I}^u$) for all $t \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{R}_+$.

Definition 2.7. The set

$$\mathbf{M}^{s(u)} = \{\eta_0 \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 : \|P_{l(r)}\eta_0\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \leq R_1, \|\eta(t, \eta_0)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \leq R_2, t \in \mathbb{R}_+\},$$

meeting the following conditions:

(i) $\mathbf{M}^{s(u)}$ is diffeomorphic to the closed sphere in $\mathbf{I}^{s(u)}$ and touches $\mathbf{I}^{s(u)}$ at the zero point;

(ii) $\|\eta(t, \eta_0)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \rightarrow 0$ ($+\infty$) at $t \rightarrow +\infty$, $\eta_0 \in \mathbf{M}^{s(u)}$

is called a *stable (unstable) invariant manifold* of equation (0.2).

Theorem 2.8. *Let the operator M be (L, p) -bounded, condition (2.5) be met, and the operator $N \in C^1(\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)$ be such that $N(0) = 0$, $N'_0 = \mathbf{O}$. Then, there exists stable \mathbf{M}^s and unstable \mathbf{M}^u invariant manifolds of equation (0.2) modeled by the stable $\mathbf{I}^s = \operatorname{im}P_l$ and unstable $\mathbf{I}^u = \operatorname{im}P_r$ invariant spaces of equation (2.4).*

Now we will outline the proof. Let the operator M be (L, p) -bounded, and the set \mathbf{M} be a smooth simple manifold. We denote $\delta : \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{M} - C^1$ -diffeomorphism, where $\delta^{-1} = P$. We fix $\omega \in \Omega$ and assume that $\mathfrak{J} = \{0\} \cup \mathbb{R}_+$, then

the solution $\eta = \eta(t)$, $t \in \mathfrak{J}$, of equation (0.2) can be presented as $\eta = \eta^1 + \delta(\eta^1)$. Here $\eta^1 = \eta^1(t)$, $t \in \mathfrak{J}$, is a solution to the equation

$$\overset{o}{\eta^1} = S\eta^1 + F(\eta^1), \quad (2.6)$$

with the operator $F = L_1^{-1}QN(\mathbb{I} + \delta)$. $S^{s(u)}$ denotes the restriction S on $\mathbf{I}^{s(u)}$. It follows from condition (2.5) that

$$\|e^{tS^{s(u)}}\|_{\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)} \leq Ce^{-\alpha t}, \quad \|Se^{tS^{s(u)}}\|_{\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2)} \leq Ce^{-\alpha t}, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}_{+(-)},$$

where $C \in [1, +\infty)$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_+$.

Let us consider the set

$$\mathbf{M}^s = \{\eta_0 \in \mathbf{M} : \eta_0 = \mathbb{I} + \delta(\mathbb{I} + \sigma)(\eta_0^s), \|\eta_0^s\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \leq \rho(2C)^{-1}\},$$

where $\sigma(\eta_0^s) = -\int_0^\infty e^{sS_u} P_r F(\eta(s, \eta_0^s)) ds$ and $\eta_0^s = P_l \eta_0^1$. The formula $D = \mathbb{I} + \delta(\mathbb{I} + \sigma)$ is used to set the C^1 -diffeomorphism of the sphere in \mathbf{U}^l and \mathbf{M}^s , wherein $(\mathbb{I} - D)(\eta) = o(\eta)$ at $\|\eta\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \rightarrow 0$. The solution $\eta(t, \eta_0)$ to equation (0.2) is as follows: $\eta(t, \eta_0) = (\mathbb{I} + \delta)\eta^1(t, P\eta_0)$ and $\delta(\eta) = o(\eta)$ at $\|\eta\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \rightarrow 0$. Then, $\|\eta(t, \eta_0)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} = \|(\mathbb{I} + \delta)\eta^1(t, P\eta_0)\|_{\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2} \rightarrow 0$ at $t \rightarrow +\infty$. Thus, the set \mathbf{M}^s is a stable invariant manifold of equation (0.2). The existence of the unstable invariant manifold is shown similarly.

3. The Stochastic Benjamin-Bona-Mahony equation

Let us consider a stochastic analog of equation (0.1). To this end, we set the spaces

$$\mathfrak{U} = \{u \in W_p^{l+2}(-\pi, \pi) : u(-\pi) = u(\pi) = 0\}, \quad \mathfrak{F} = W_p^l(-\pi, \pi),$$

where $l \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{N}$, $p \in [2, +\infty)$. The space \mathfrak{U} is continuously and densely embedded in the space \mathfrak{F} at $n \geq 3$ and $2 \leq p \leq 4/(n-2) + 2$. The basis in the Hilbert space $W_p^{l+2}(-\pi, \pi)$ is the sequence $\{\sin kx\}$ of the eigenfunctions of the Laplace operator Δ with the spectrum $\sigma(\Delta) = -k^2$. Let the sequence $\{\chi_k\} \subset \mathbf{L}_2$ ($\{\zeta_k\} \subset \mathbf{L}_2$) be uniformly bounded. The elements of the space of \mathbf{K} -values $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ ($\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$) will be the vectors

$$\chi = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \chi_k \sin kx \quad \left(\zeta = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \zeta_k \sin kx \right),$$

where the positive monotonic sequence $\{\lambda_k\}$ is such that $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k < +\infty$. We can choose $\lambda_k = |-k^2|^{-m} = k^{-2m}$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, as the sequence $\mathbf{K} = \{\lambda_k\}$, wherein the series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{-2m}$ converges at any $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

Stochastic equation (0.1) will be considered as a special case of the

$$L \overset{o}{\chi} = M\chi + N(\chi), \quad (3.1)$$

with the operators

$$L = \lambda - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2}, \quad M = \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial^2}, \quad N : \chi \rightarrow -\chi_x \chi.$$

The operators $L, M : \mathfrak{U} \rightarrow \mathfrak{F}$ are constructed as linear and continuous. According to lemma 2.1, the operators $L, M : \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ are linear and continuous.

The L -spectrum of the operator M is as follows:

$$\sigma^L(M) = \left\{ -\frac{\nu n^2}{n^2 + \lambda} : n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{l : \lambda = l^2\} \right\},$$

and, hence, bounded. Since the Frechet derivative of the operator N at the point χ is

$$N'_\chi \psi : \psi \rightarrow \chi \psi_x + \chi_x \psi,$$

and $N(0) = 0, N'_0 \equiv \mathbb{O}$. The following lemma is correct.

Lemma 3.1. (i) For $n \geq 3$ and $2 \leq p \leq 4/(n-2) + 2$, the operator M is $(L, 0)$ -bounded;

(ii) the operator $N \in C^1(\mathfrak{U}; \mathfrak{F}), N(0) = 0, N'_0 \equiv \mathbb{O}$.

Let us construct the set \mathbf{M} and the space $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2$ having the following form

$$\mathbf{M} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, \lambda \neq -n^2; \\ \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (\nu \chi_{xx} - \chi_x \chi) \sin l x dx = 0, \lambda = l^2\}; \end{array} \right.$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, \lambda \neq -n^2; \\ \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \chi \sin l x dx = 0, \lambda = l^2\}. \end{array} \right.$$

[4] showed that the phase space of equation (0.1) consists of two parts, each of which is a simple Banach C^∞ -manifold. Accordingly, let us assume that $\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2$ is the operator kernel $\ker L = \text{span}\{\sin l x\}$.

Then $\chi = a \sin l x + v$, where $v \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2, a = \lambda_l \chi_l$. The point $\chi \in \mathfrak{M}$ is correct when

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (\nu(a \sin l x + v)_{xx} - (a \sin l x + v)_x (a \sin l x + v)) \sin l x dx = 0$$

or

$$-a(l^2 \nu + \frac{1}{4} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v (\sin l x)_x^2 dx) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v v_x \sin l x dx. \quad (3.2)$$

Equation (3.2) has an unambiguous solution at

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v (\sin l x)_x^2 dx = -4l^2 \nu, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v \sin 2l x = -8l \nu.$$

Then $\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 = \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{11}\mathbf{L}_2 \cup \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{12}\mathbf{L}_2$, where

$$\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{11}\mathbf{L}_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, \lambda \neq -n^2; \\ \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v \sin 2l x dx > -8l \nu, \lambda = l^2\}, \end{array} \right.$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{12}\mathbf{L}_2 = \begin{cases} \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2, & \lambda \neq -n^2; \\ \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^1\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v \sin 2lxdx < -8l\nu, \lambda = l^2\}. \end{cases}$$

The expression $\delta : \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{11}\mathbf{L}_2 \cup \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}^{12}\mathbf{L}_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{M}$ is as follows

$$\delta(v) = v + \frac{8 \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} vv_x \sin lxdx}{-8al^2\nu - \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} v \sin 2lxdx}.$$

δ is C^∞ -diffeomorphic, wherein $\delta^{-1} = P$ with the projection

$$P = \begin{cases} \mathbb{I}, & \lambda \neq -n^2; \\ \mathbb{I} - \langle \cdot, \sin lx \rangle \sin lx, & \lambda = l^2. \end{cases}$$

Then, according to theorem 2.4, the following theorem is correct.

Theorem 3.2. *For all $\lambda, \nu \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ the phase space of equation (3.1) is the union of two simple Banach C^∞ -manifolds modeled by the space \mathfrak{U}^1 .*

We hereinafter use \mathbf{M} to denote the component of this set that contains the zero point. When studying stability, we confine ourselves to the case of the positive parameter ν . The L -spectrum of the operator M consists of two members

$$\sigma_l^L(M) = \left\{ -\frac{\nu n^2}{n^2 + \lambda} : n^2 > -\lambda \right\}, \quad \sigma_r^L(M) = \left\{ -\frac{\nu n^2}{n^2 + \lambda} : n^2 < -\lambda \right\}.$$

Then the finite-dimensional space $\mathbf{U}^s = \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \chi \sin mxdx = 0, m^2 > -\lambda\}$, $\dim \mathbf{U}^s = \max\{m^2 > -\lambda\}$, and the infinite-dimensional space $\mathbf{U}^u = \{\chi \in \mathbf{U}_{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{L}_2 : \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \chi \sin mxdx = 0, m^2 < -\lambda\}$, $\dim \mathbf{U}^u = \dim \mathbf{U}^s + \dim \ker L$, will be stable and unstable invariant spaces of the linear member of equation (3.1), respectively.

Theorem 3.3. *For any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, $\nu \in \mathbb{R}_+$ equation (3.1) in the vicinity of the zero point has finite-dimensional unstable \mathbf{M}^s and infinite-dimensional stable \mathbf{M}^u invariant manifolds modeled by the spaces \mathbf{U}^s and \mathbf{U}^u , respectively.*

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